

Application of Differential Thermal Analysis to the Study of Solid Catalyst Systems: $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-ZnO}$, $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-ZrO}_2$, $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MgO}$, and $\text{ZrO}_2\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$

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The technique of differential thermal analysis (D.T.A.) has been applied to the binary oxide catalyst systems like $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-ZnO}$, $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-ZrO}_2$, $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MgO}$, and $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3\text{-ZrO}_2$ with a view to correlating the D.T.A. data with the surface area and catalytic activity of the systems. Differential thermal analysis has indicated a high mutual protective action against crystallisation in each of the systems.

The composition showing the maximum protection against crystallisation in the respective system has been found to have the maximum surface area and catalytic activity for the one-step catalytic conversion of ethanol to butadiene.

The usefulness of the technique of differential thermal analysis (D.T.A.) for the structural studies of solid catalysts has already been established by Bhattacharyya and his co-workers¹⁻⁶ by carrying out the differential thermal analyses of a large number of single, binary, and ternary catalyst systems. The present communication deals with the D.T.A. data of four new binary oxide catalyst systems: (A) alumina-zinc oxide ($\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-ZnO}$), (B) alumina-zirconia ($\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-ZrO}_2$), (C) alumina-magnesia ($\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-MgO}$), and (D) ferric oxide-zirconia ($\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3\text{-ZrO}_2$).

The influence of catalyst composition on the thermograms has been thoroughly studied in each case. An attempt has also been made to correlate the D.T.A. data and surface area with the catalytic activity, exhibited by the samples in the one-step catalytic conversion of ethanol to butadiene⁷⁻⁹.

EXPERIMENTAL

The apparatus and the experimental procedure for D.T.A. and those for surface area measurement have already been published by Bhattacharyya *et al.*^{1,10}. The individual

1. Bhattacharyya and Ramachandran, *Bull. Nat. Inst. Sci., India*, 1959, No. 12, 23 (Proc. of the Symposium on Contact Catalysis, 1956, Calcutta).
2. Bhattacharyya and Kameswari, *ibid.*, p. 46.
3. Bhattacharyya, Ramachandran, and Ghosh, "Advances in Catalysis", Academic Press, New York, 1957, IX, 114; Proc. 1st Int. Congr. on Catalysis, 1956, Philadelphia.
4. Bhattacharyya and Kameswari, *J. chim. phys.*, 1959, 56, 823.
5. Bhattacharyya *et al.*, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1960, 214, 191.
6. Bhattacharyya and Ganguly, *Proc. Nat. Inst. Sci., India*, 1961, 27A, 588.
7. *Idem*, *J. Appl. Chem.*, London, 1962, 12, 97.
8. *Idem*, *ibid.*, 1962, 12, 105.
9. *Idem*, Proc. 2nd Int. Cong. on Catalysis, Paris, 1960, III, 2385.
10. Ghosh *et al.*, *Bull. Nat. Inst. Sci., India*, 1959, No. 12, 15; Proc. of the Symposium on Contact Catalysis, 1956, Calcutta.

oxides in the form hydrous gel were precipitated from the solution of the respective metal nitrate. The binary hydrous gels were prepared by coprecipitation from the mixed solutions of nitrates (mixed in definite, precalculated ratio so as to conform to the ultimate desired composition), with ammonium hydroxide. The concentration of the nitrate solutions was kept at 0.5M. The precipitated gels were washed free of nitrate ions and oven-dried at 110° for 24 hr. (unless mentioned otherwise) and then powdered to -100 to +120 B.S. mesh size.

The activity of the catalysts was measured as a function of the process yield of butadiene in the one-step catalytic conversion of ethanol to butadiene. The procedure and experimental arrangement adopted for this reaction have been published earlier⁹.

DISCUSSION

(A) System Al_2O_3 -ZnO

The results of D. T. A. of pure Al_2O_3 and ZnO gels and also their various binary combinations are graphically represented in Fig. 1.

FIG 1. Thermograms.

FIG 2. Surface area and catalytic activity.

Pure Al_2O_3 gel shows two endothermic peaks, one at 120° and the other at 330°. The former is due to dehydration and the latter indicates the crystal-

lisation of amorphous Al_2O_3 to its γ -variety. There is no further phase change up to 900° .

The pure ZnO gel exhibited three endothermic peaks at 80° , 200° , and 280° . The first one is probably due to loss of adsorbed water and the second one indicates the decomposition of $\text{Zn}(\text{OH})_2$ to hydrated ZnO. The third endothermal effect is due to dehydration of the hydrated ZnO. Bhattacharyya and Ramachandran¹ reported similar observations with ZnO gel, prepared by various other ways.

From the study of the thermograms of the mixed Al_2O_3 -ZnO gels, it is clear that ZnO, even when present to the extent of 20%, inhibits crystallisation of Al_2O_3 completely.

The samples containing more than 20% Al_2O_3 shows only one endothermic peak, extending roughly up to 250° . The stopwise dehydration of the ZnO gel is no longer observed.

The surface areas of three samples containing 80, 60, and 40% Al_2O_3 were measured by B. E. T. technique and these were found to be 147.9, 227.9, and $152.2\text{m}^2/\text{g}$. (all samples being preheated to 500°) respectively. It was further observed that the surface areas of these samples remained practically constant within 400 - 800° .

In this series, Al_2O_3 -ZnO(60:40) was found to be the most active catalyst for the one-step catalytic conversion of ethanol to butadiene both in the fixed and fluidised beds^{6,9}. The correlation between the surface area and catalytic activity will be evident from Fig. 2 and Table I.

TABLE I

D.T.A., surface area, and catalytic activity of Al_2O_3 -ZnO.

Composition (Al_2O_3 : ZnO).	Endothermic peak temp. (Formation of γ - Al_2O_3).	Upper temp. limit of endother- mic trough for dehydration.	Surface area (m^2/g).	%Process yield of butadiene.*	
				Fixed bed.	Fluidised bed.
100 : 0	330°	150°	205.0	13.7	8.4
80 : 20	Absent	250°	147.9	33.6	31.5
60 : 40	"	250°	227.9	55.8	72.8
40 : 60	"	250°	152.2	30.0	55.5
20 : 80	"	Two peaks exten- ding to (i) 240° (ii) 360° (250 - 360°)	..	25.6	Not tried
0 : 100	"	Three peaks with mean tempera- tures 80° , 200° , 280°	..	4.2	Not tried

* Conditions of the experiment:

Wt. of the catalyst	..	..	20 g.	52 g.
Temperature	..	..	425°	425°
Rate of delivery of ethanol (ml/hr.-g.)	..	..	1.875	2.58

(B) System $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-ZrO}_2$

The pure Al_2O_3 and ZrO_2 gels and the mixed gels containing 90, 70, 50, 30, and 10% Al_2O_3 were prepared by the usual method described before.

Fig. 3 represents the thermograms of pure ZrO_2 and also those for the different $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-ZrO}_2$ gels. The thermal characteristics of Al_2O_3 have already been discussed.

FIG 3

Pure ZrO_2 is characterised by a large endothermic peak at about 160° due to expulsion of water, followed by a sharp exothermic peak at 430° , corresponding to the transformation of a amorphous ZrO_2 to the monoclinic variety. Bohm¹¹ reported the temperature of

11. *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1925, 149, 217.

crystallisation of zirconia gel to be 440° from his X-ray-studies. Incorporation of 10% Al₂O₃ to the ZrO₂ gel shifts the exothermic crystallisation peak to 710°. The crystallisation of ZrO₂ is retarded even to a higher temperature with higher concentration of alumina in the mixed gel. The surface area of the mixed oxide is found to increase with increase in Al₂O₃ content (Table II) and reaches a maximum of 262.1 m²/g. for the composition Al₂O₃:ZrO₂=70:30. This composition exhibits the maximum protection against crystallisation.

TABLE II

D.T.A., surface area, and catalytic activity of Al₂O₃-ZrO₂.

Gel composition (Al ₂ O ₃ : ZrO ₂).	Peak temperature.		Surface area (m ² /g.).	%Process yield of butadiene.*
	Endothermic. (Formation of -Al ₂ O ₃).	Exothermic. (Formation of monoclinic ZrO ₂).		
100 : 0	330°	..	205.0	13.70
90 : 10	300°	..	234.9	18.70 ^a
70 : 30	300°	825	262.1	28.03 ^b
50 : 50	300°	825	261.7	18.30 ^c
30 : 70	300°	750	249.6	11.43 ^d
10 : 90	Absent (only dehydration trough is present)	710	231.1	9.00
0 : 100	Do	430	162.9	9.40

*Conditions of the experiment:

Wt. of the catalyst 20 g.
Temp. 425°
Rate of delivery
of ethanol(ml/hr.-g.) 1.875

Catalyst composition (Al₂O₃: ZrO₂):

a—92.8 : 17.2
b—64.4 : 35.6
c—44.1 : 55.9
d—23.2 : 76.8

All the gels show a low-temperature endothermal effect ranging from 75° to 225° due to expulsion of adsorbed water. Further, all the gels, excepting the one containing 90% ZrO₂, show another endothermic peak, the magnitude of which is found to increase with increasing Al₂O₃-content at temperatures around 300° due to conversion of amorphous Al₂O₃ to γ -Al₂O₃.

For the one-step catalytic conversion of ethanol to butadiene, slightly different compositions of Al₂O₃-ZrO₂ mixed oxides were used. These compositions are recorded in the footnote of Table II.

The catalyst having the composition Al₂O₃: ZrO₂=64.4:35.6 shows the highest activity (Table II). This composition of the mixed oxide is near to the one exhibiting maximum surface area and high protective action against crystallisation.

(C) System Al₂O₃-MgO

The thermograms of the individual gels (*i.e.* Al₂O₃ and MgO) and also of the binary mixtures of Al₂O₃ and MgO of different compositions are shown in Fig. 4.

Pure MgO shows one endothermic trough at 350° (range $200-400^\circ$) and the other at 700° (range $550-800^\circ$). The low-temperature endothermic effect is probably due to the loss of water. The high-temperature endothermal change is probably due to minor lattice reorganisation.

FIG. 4

Anderson¹³ and Mellor¹⁴ reported that some of the chemical properties of MgO (like hydration, adsorption, etc.) and also its density considerably changed with the rise in temperature although the general crystal structure was not affected. The above workers suggested that such changes in physical and chemical properties were caused initially by dehydration, which was later followed by lattice reorientation at a high temperature.

Thus the present D. T. A. results for MgO find excellent support from the previous work in this line.

13. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 87, 257.

14. "A Comprehensive Treatise on Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry", Longmans, Green & Co., London, 1948, IV, 283.

The optimum temperature for the conversion of ethanol to butadiene, using MgO as the catalyst, was found to be 425°, i.e., just after complete removal of water from the catalyst (at 420°).

Crystallisation of Al₂O₃ was found to be retarded to higher temperatures with incorporation of MgO. For the sample containing 80% MgO, the endothermic peak for crystallisation of Al₂O₃ was absent within the temperature range studied (900°).

The initial endothermal trough present in each case is due to expulsion of water from the sample. With the increase in concentration of MgO in the samples, these endothermal troughs extend more towards higher temperatures.

Al₂O₃:MgO (80:20) was found to be the best catalyst in this series for the one-step conversion of ethanol to butadiene both in fixed and fluidised beds. The optimum temperature of reaction was 425°, which coincided exactly with the onset of crystallisation of Al₂O₃. The activity of the catalyst fell down considerably above this temperature, perhaps due to decrease in the surface area resulting from the crystallisation of Al₂O₃.

Catalytic activities of the other combinations were adversely affected, probably due to presence of strongly bound water which could be completely expelled only at a very high temperature. The correlation between catalytic activity and D.T.A. data is shown in Table III.

TABLE III
D.T.A. and catalytic activity of Al₂O₃-MgO.

Composition (Al ₂ O ₃ : MgO).	Endothermic peak temp. (Formation of γ -Al ₂ O ₃).	Upper temp. limit of endothermic trough for dehydration.	% Process yield of butadiene.*	
			Fixed bed.	Fluidised bed.
100 : 0	330°	150°	13.7	8.4
80 : 20	430°	320°	20.7	35.3
60 : 40	550°	Two troughs (320° and 480°)	16.6	17.6
40 : 60	550° (very small peak)	500°	14.2	17.3
20 : 80	Absent	500°	13.7	Not tried
0 : 100	..	Two troughs (400° and 800°)	17.8	Not tried

*Conditions of the experiment:

Wt. of the catalyst	..	20g.	23.4 g.
Temperature	..	400°	425°
Rate of delivery of ethanol, (ml/hr.-g.)	..	1.875	5.69

(D) System ZrO₂-Fe₂O₃

The binary hydrous zirconia and ferric oxide gels containing 10, 20, 40, 60, and 80% ZrO₂ were prepared by the method outlined earlier. One part of each gel was air-dried, whereas the other was oven-dried.

Other methods of preparation of the gels were also tried and in each case the thermograms were found to be exactly of the same type.

The thermograms of the oven-dried zirconia-ferric oxide gels, individual as well as mixed, are illustrated in Fig. 5.

FIG. 5

The thermogram of pure ZrO_2 gel has already been discussed. Pure Fe_2O_3 gel shows one endothermic peak at 180° ($100-270^\circ$) corresponding to the loss of adsorbed water and an exothermic peak at 420° ($370-450^\circ$) indicating crystallisation.

All the mixed gels exhibit excellent mutual protective action against crystallisation, *i.e.*, the crystallisation of ZrO_2 is retarded by the presence of Fe_2O_3 and *vice versa*. The extent of this mutual protective efficiency depends on the relative concentration of the individual oxides in the mixed gels.

All the gels exhibit dehydration peaks between 100° and 300° . The presence of 20% Fe_2O_3 in zirconia retards crystallisation of the latter, which occurs at 544° ($500-600^\circ$) only. On the other hand, addition of 10% zirconia to ferric oxide shifts the exothermal

crystallisation peak of the latter to 564° ($500-650^{\circ}$). This phenomenon of mutual protective action is maximum for the binary zirconia-ferric oxide (40:60) gel, which shows the exothermic effect at a temperature as high as 728° (range $660-775^{\circ}$). Similar mutual protection against crystallisation has been observed previously by Bhattacharyya and co-workers¹⁻⁶ in other mixed gels and also by Weiser *et al.*¹⁵.

The air-dried samples of zirconia-ferric oxide behaved in a similar way, the only difference being the larger magnitude of the dehydration endothermic peaks. The replacement of ammonia by sodium hydroxide as precipitant did not affect the above mentioned thermal characteristics in any way. But the mutual protective action against crystallisation, observed in the case of coprecipitates, was totally absent in the case of the mechanically mixed gels.

The phenomenon of the mutual protection against crystallisation is further assured by measuring the surface area of the different $ZrO_2-Fe_2O_3$ gels, preheated to different temperatures. It is expected that the surface area would remain fairly constant so long as crystallisation does not set in. The observations recorded below will testify the expectation.

The surface area of $ZrO_2-Fe_2O_3$ (80:20) gel was found to be 242.2, 235.0, 228.7, and 60.9 $m^2/g.$ when the sample was heated to 375° , 425° , 480° , and 580° respectively, the last temperature being above the crystallisation temperature (544°). The surface area of the pure zirconia gel was found to undergo abrupt decrease above 350° , the crystallisation temperature. In the case of the ZrO_2 gel with 20% Fe_2O_3 , the surface area did not vary much with temperature in the region of $375-480^{\circ}$, whereas there was an abrupt fall at 580° , thereby substantiating the crystallisation peak observed between 500° and 600° .

TABLE IV

D.T.A., surface area, and catalytic activity of $ZrO_2-Fe_2O_3$.

Composition ($ZrO_2 : Fe_2O_3$).	Exothermic peak temp. (Crystallisation of Fe_2O_3).	Surface area ($m^2/g.$).	Process yield of butadiene.*
100 : 0	..	177.5	23.15
80 : 20	544°	223.0	32.09
60 : 40	674°	245.6	34.48
40 : 60	728°	259.8	38.32
20 : 80	720°	194.6	29.22
10 : 90	564°	..	..
0 : 10	420°	23.0	14.33

*Conditions of the experiment:

Wt. of the catalyst ..	20 g.
Temperature ..	450°
Rate of delivery of ethanol (ml/hr.-g.) ..	1.875

At any temperature level, pronounced surface properties and catalytic activity may be expected in the gel composition showing maximum mutual protective action. It is evident from Table IV and Fig. 5 that the mutual protective action, as determined by

differential thermal analysis, is maximum for the gel with 40% ZrO_2 . The surface area of the gels, all heated to 350° , increases from the extreme ends of the composition range and reaches a maximum for the gel containing 40% ZrO_2 . Correspondingly, the highest process yield of butadiene is obtained when the gel composition $ZrO_2 : Fe_2O_3 = 40 : 60$, activated at 450° , is used as a catalyst.

The data recorded herein show the remarkable correlation between D. T. A. data with surface area and catalytic activity of the single as well as binary oxide catalyst systems. Particularly, the phenomenon of mutual protection against crystallisation, as observed in the different mixed gels, assures large surface area of the gels at a comparatively high temperature range. Consequently, the catalytic activity of the gels, which is in general a function of their surface area, is found to increase or at least remains constant at higher temperatures. This significant observation will successfully lead not only to the choice of the most active catalyst composition of a system, but also it will fix the optimum temperature range for a catalyst.

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